

A NOTE ON THE SMARANDACHE DIVISOR SEQUENCES

(Amarnath Murthy ,S.E. (E &T), Well Logging Services, Oil And Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. ,Sabarmati, Ahmedbad, India- 380005.)

ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION (**SFP**) , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r) = F'(N)$,where

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

In [2] we have defined SMARANDACHE DIVISOR SEQUENCES as follows

$$P_n = \{ x \mid d(x) = n \} \quad , \quad d(x) = \text{number of divisors of } n.$$

$$P_1 = \{1\}$$

$$P_2 = \{ x \mid x \text{ is a prime} \}$$

$$P_3 = \{ x \mid x = p^2, p \text{ is a prime} \}$$

$$P_4 = \{ x \mid x = p^3 \text{ or } x = p_1 p_2, p, p_1, p_2 \text{ are primes} \}$$

Let F_1 be a SFP of N . Let $\Psi_{F_1} = \{y \mid d(y) = N\}$, generated by the SFP F_1 of N . It has been shown in Ref. [3] that each SFP generates some elements of Ψ or P_n . Here each SFP generates infinitely many elements of P_n . Similarly $\Psi_{F_1}, \Psi_{F_2}, \Psi_{F_3}, \dots, \Psi_{F'(N)}$, are defined. It is evident that all these F_k 's are disjoint and also

$$P_N = \cup \Psi_{F_k} \quad 1 \leq k \leq F'(N).$$

THEOREM(7.1) There are $F'(N)$ disjoint and exhaustive subsets in which P_N can be decomposed.

PROOF: Let $\theta \in P_N$, and let it be expressed in canonical form as follows

$$\theta = \begin{matrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 & \dots & \alpha_r \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & \dots & p_r \end{matrix}$$

Then $d(\theta) = (\alpha_1+1)(\alpha_2+1)(\alpha_3+1) \dots (\alpha_r+1)$

Hence $\theta \in \Psi_{F_k}$ for some k where F_k is given by

$$N = (\alpha_1+1)(\alpha_2+1)(\alpha_3+1) \dots (\alpha_r+1)$$

Again if $\theta \in \Psi_{F_s}$, and $\theta \in \Psi_{F_t}$ then from unique factorisation theorem F_s and F_t are identical SFPs of N .

REFERENCES:

[1] "Amarnath Murthy", 'Generalization Of Partition Function, Introducing 'Smarandache Factor Partition', SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.

[2] "Amarnath Murthy", 'Some New Smarandache Sequences, Functions And Partitions', SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.

[3] "Amarnath Murthy", 'Some more Ideas on SFPS. SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.

[4] "The Florentine Smarandache" Special Collection, Archives of American Mathematics, Centre for American History, University of Texas at Austin, USA.